

(1 and 2) by two-stage preparative tlc (Polyamide DC₈; C₈H₈, MeOH, EtCOMe=4,3,3; R_f, 0.30 and 0.32 and microcrystalline cellulose; 60% HOAc; R_f, 0.55 and 0.70). Compound 1 was identified as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-6-O-β-D-glucosylflavone (6-glucosylxyluteolin, stereolensin) by uv, ¹H nmr, FABMS, hydrolysis with acid as well as the enzyme β-glucosidase in agreement with the earlier report⁴ and confirmed by co-R_f with an authentic sample.

Compound 2 could not be crystallised. Its solution in MeOH had R_f characteristic of a flavone glycoside^{6,7}. It underwent hydrolysis (0.5 M HCl, 30 min) to yield scutellarein and D-glucose. Identity of both the products were established beyond doubt by spectral analysis and glc comparison of the silylated derivatives with authentic compounds.

The glucoside exhibited uv absorption (intensity relative to most intense peak as 1.00) at (MeOH) 247sh, 271 (0.69), 292sh, 334 (1.00); (NaOMe) 257sh, 274 (0.58), 326 (0.38), 394 (1.00); (AlCl₃) 254sh, 280 (0.62), 288sh, 302 (0.65), 358 (1.00), 385sh; (AlCl₃-HCl) 253sh, 278 (0.67), 300 (0.71), 351 (1.00), 386sh; (NaOAc) 249sh, 273 (1.00), 289 (0.60), 300sh, 361 (0.80); (NaOAc-H₃BO₃) 249sh, 272 (1.00), 292 (0.70), 298 (0.63), 347 (0.82). Its ¹H nmr spectra (350 MHz, DMSO-d₆ and DMSO-d₆+1 drop of TFA, internal standard TMS) exhibited signals at δ 7.90 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 6.91 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 6.70 (1H, s, H-8), 6.41 (1H, s, H-3), 5.08 (1H, s, H-1 of glucose: appearing at 4.90 as 1H, d, J 8.5 Hz) with TFA), 4.95 and 4.67 (3H and 2H, m each, other glucose protons).

The uv spectra of 2 in MeOH and in presence of diagnostic reagents were very similar to 6-O-methylscutellarein⁸ and different from 7-O-methylscutellarein⁹. The AlCl₃ and AlCl₃/HCl spectra, besides indicating⁹ a blocked 6-OH, exhibited a shoulder around 385 nm which appears to be characteristic of 6-O-glycosylation on the basis of a similar observation earlier⁸. ¹H nmr spectra (resolution improved by adding one drop of TFA to DMSO-d₆ solution) showed signals characteristic of scutellarein and D-glucose moieties. The coupling constant (8.2 Hz) of H-1 of glucose revealed the β-configuration of the sugar. The negative ion FABMS of the glucoside exhibited peaks at 447 (M-H)⁻ and 285 (aglycone-H)⁻. Pyrolysis positive chemical ionisation (NH₃)MS with characteristic peaks at m/z 287 (aglycone+H)⁺ (100%), 180 (isobaric ion of glucose, replacing anomeric OH by NH₃) (100%), 162 (180-H₂O, 15%) and 145 (162-NH₃, 14%) and negative chemical ionisation (Cl⁻)MS with supporting complimentary peaks⁶ at m/z 285 (aglycone-H)⁻, 215 (glucose+Cl)⁻ (8%), 197 (215-H₂O, 100%), 179 (197-H₂O, 16%), 143 (glucose-H-2H₂O) (22%) further confirmed the nature of the aglycone as well as sugar. Based on the above data, 2 was characterised as 6-O-β-D-glucosyl scutellarein. The ring size of the sugar could not be established owing to paucity of material for ¹³C nmr analysis¹⁰. To our knowledge, this is the second record of occur-

ence of 6-O-glycosylscutellarein; the first being in *Haplopappus rengifoanus*¹¹ (Asteraceae). Contrary to earlier observations^{1,6,8} both the compounds, 6-O-glucosylxyluteolin and 6-O-glucosylapigenin were hydrolysed by β-glucosidase indicating that 6-O-glycosylation cannot be implicated in non-hydrolysability of these compounds. Successful β-glucosidase hydrolysis was also reported on the compound from *H. rengifoanus*. The ¹H nmr, negative FABMS as well as positive and negative CIMS data on this compound are reported for the first time. The earlier workers reported the ¹H nmr data on trimethyl silyl derivative.

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Quantitative Determination of Metronidazole in Drug Preparations by Indirect Acid-Base Titration Method

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An indirect acid-base method was employed for the quantitative determination of metronidazole in pharmaceutical dosage forms and compared with the other methods. The samples assayed were found to contain not less than 97.80±0.12% of the drug and the technique is rapid and selective.

TABLE 1

Sl no	Method	Metronidazole			
		Powder (Reference)	Injection (5 mg ml ⁻¹)	Tablets (200 mg)	Tablets (Vaginal, 200 mg)
1. Indirect - Acid Base Titration ^a					
(a)	Average % recovered	98.28	97.66	98.02	97.29
	Std. deviation	±0.085	±0.24	±0.12	±0.075
	Coeff. of variation	0.085	0.245	0.122	0.077
(b)	Average wt. (mg) recovered	496.39	4.88 ^c	196.02	194.61
	Std. deviation	±0.43	±0.012	±0.25	±0.150
	Coeff. of variation	0.43	0.012	0.25	0.150
2. Non-aqueous titration ^b					
(a)	Average % recovered	100.10	98.90	98.47	96.63
	Std. deviation	±0.68	±0.80	±0.38	±0.40
	Coeff. of variation	0.679	0.80	0.38	0.40

^aPresent work. ^bOfficial method⁵. ^cmg cm⁻².

Metronidazole (2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole-1-ethanol) has found wide use in the treatment of trichomoniasis, amoebiasis and giardiasis¹. Analytical procedures, viz. non-aqueous titration², the uv spectroscopy³ and colourimetry³ have been reported for the analysis of metronidazole in tablet preparations. The present study was undertaken to investigate the possibility of using the indirect acid-base method⁴ involving determination of hydroxyl group present in metronidazole and to correlate the results with the existing methods and to extend it to its major metabolite and the injection preparation.

The hydroxyl reaction is acid-catalysed by perchloric acid. The acid produced and the acid catalyst are titrated with a standard base using a suitable indicator against reagent blank.

Experimental

Pure reference standard metronidazole was received as a gift sample from May & Baker (U.K.). Three different commercial brands of metronidazole tablets and an injection preparation were procured. All reagents used were of AnalaR (U.K.) grade.

Standard preparation: Pure metronidazole powder (500 mg) was dissolved in minimum amount of ethyl acetate and acetylating mixture (acetic anhydride and perchloric acid in ethyl acetate) (~5 ml) was added to it. The mixture was heated at 50° on a water-bath for 10 min and then cooled. Pyridine-water (3 : 1) mixture (10 ml) was added to it which hydrolysed the excess acetic anhydride. The acid produced and acid catalyst were then titrated with standard methanolic 0.5 N sodium hydroxide using thymol blue as the indicator. The procedure was repeated using 5 ml of acetylating mixture without the drug sample. The difference in the two titrations corresponded to the amount of hydroxyl group present in the drug sample.

Injection preparation: The above method of acetylation using perchloric acid as catalyst was also

employed with the injection preparation using 20 ml for each titration which is equivalent to 100 mg of metronidazole.

Tablet preparation: Twenty tablets of metronidazole were weighed and reduced to a fine powder. The powder (equivalent to 200 mg of metronidazole) was dissolved in purified water and the solution filtered. The clear filtrate was extracted with a mixture (3×20 ml) of diethyl ether and acetone (1 : 1), and shaken vigorously. The organic extracts were combined together and treated anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove traces of moisture. The solvent was evaporated at 50° to obtain the dry powdered drug. Three different brands of tablet preparations were assayed.

The acetylation mixture was then added to the dried drug powder and the rest of the procedure was the same as in the standard preparation.

Results and Discussion

The present OH of metronidazole in the sample was determined according to the method described by Viel⁴. The results (Table 1) show that the indirect acid-base titration method gave values comparable to USP method². In addition, the method is quite inexpensive, quick and less cumbersome as it did not involve prior preparation of standard perchloric acid solution and/or any sophisticated instrument.

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